

Home Automation Using Node-MCU WIFI Module

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Abstract - This project presents the design and implementation of an advance home automation system that uses WIFI technology as a network infrastructure to connect its various locations. The planning process consists of two main parts; The first part is the server (web server), which is the basis of the control system that controls and monitors the user's home. Users and system administrators can control and manage system code locally (LAN) or remotely (Internet). The second part is the hardware interface module, which provides the necessary interface to the sensors and actuators of the home automation system. Unlike most of the home automation systems available on the market, the application process is scalable and a single server can manage many hardware interface modules as long as they are within the scope of the WIFI network. The system supports many home automation devices such as power management devices and security devices. In terms of scalability and flexibility, off-the-shelf systems are better than commercial home automation systems.

Keywords— Node-Mcu, Relay, Blynk IOT, Network Gride, Push Button, Arduino

1.0 Introduction

This project is designed to create an advanced home automation system using a web server and Wi-Fi technology. This device can be turned on/off and the sensors [1] can be read from a personal computer (PC) via Wi-Fi. Automation is a word often written in electronics. The desire for automation has brought many revolutions in existing technologies. These technologies are more important than others because of their ease of use. These can be used to replace existing switches that can create sparks in your home and less often cause fires. Considering the advantages of Wi-Fi, advanced automation systems have been developed to manage home electronics. Wi-Fi (short for Wireless Fidelity) is a wireless technology that uses radio frequency to transmit data over the air [2]. Wi-Fi. The original speed is 1mbps to 2mbps. Wi-Fi transmits data in the 2.4 GHz frequency band. It uses the concept of frequency division multiplexing technology. The range of Wi-Fi technology is 40-300 feet [3] The electronic control device in the project is Arduino UNO [4] The data sent from the PC via Wi-Fi will be received from the Wi-Fi module connected to the Arduino. uno. The Arduino UNO reads the data and determines the change of the electronic device connected to it by sending it.[5] When people think of home automation, most people think of living in a smart home: remote control for every appliance, automatic cooking, automatic air conditioning, automatic heating of the shower and automatic shutters, night comes. In a sense, home automation is synonymous with smart home. All of them bring a good lifestyle and make your lives easier and faster. [6] 2006 S. M. Anamul Haq, S. MM.

Kamruzzaman and M.D. Ashraful Islam has announced a system called Time-Based Voice-Based Smart Home Appliance Control System that uses a personal computer to control home appliances. The system uses Visual Basic 6.0 as its programming language and uses the Microsoft Speech Engine for speech recognition. You can control your device using a timer or voice commands. Don't cook, turn on the air conditioner, heat up the shower, and close the windows. In a sense, home automation is synonymous with smart home. All of them bring a good lifestyle and make your lives easier and faster. [7] In their paper Tan, Lee, and Soh (2002) they proposed the creation of an Internet-based system to allow monitoring of critical systems of distributed control systems (DCS) [8] This article presents the hardware and software design. use the decision so that users can remotely access and access different systems of DCS [9]. This document presents hardware and software design considerations to enable users to access different DCS systems, automate rice cookers remotely and efficiently, automatically operate air conditioner, heat shower only, and shade windows at night. In a way, home automation is synonymous with the smart home. All of them lead to a better lifestyle and make your life easier and faster [10]

2.0 Circuit Diagram

Fig. 1 Circuit Diagram of Home Automation System

2.1 Components

ESP8266 is a Wi-Fi enabled microcontroller that can be used in home automation projects. How it works includes the following steps: Connect the ESP8266 to a local Wi-Fi network: The ESP8266 can connect to a local Wi-Fi network, enabling it to communicate with other devices on the network such as smartphones and laptops. Send commands to ESP8266: Users can send commands to the ESP8266 to control connected devices such as lights, fans, and thermostats using the mobile app or web interface. Functional Description: The ESP8266 receives and processes commands and communicates with connected devices using digital signals such as GPIO (General Purpose Input/Output) pins. Device operation: When a command is received, the ESP8266 connected device can turn on or off the light, adjust the temperature, etc. can perform its actions. Send status updates: The ESP8266 can send status updates to the user such as current temperature or status of connected devices. As a result, the ESP8266 acts as a bridge between the local Wi-Fi network and connected devices, allowing these devices to be controlled and monitored remotely.

3.0 Working Principal

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Fig. 2 Connection Diagram of Home Automation System

The ESP8266 is a low-cost Wi-Fi MCU chip with full TCP/IP stack and MCU features. It works by connecting to a Wi-Fi network and sending and receiving data to and from the internet over that connection. It can be programmed as a stand-alone device or as part of a larger system. It is powered by 3.3V and has GPIO pins for interacting with external devices. Blynk is a mobile application development platform for the Internet of Things (IoT). You can monitor and control IoT devices through mobile apps without coding and installing complex servers. Connect to your device via Wi-Fi and transfer your data to the Blynk cloud servers, and your data will be sent to the mobile app. You can install virtual buttons, sliders, images, and other widgets in your app to control and display information from your device. Blynk also provides APIs for many programming languages, making it easy to integrate with your IoT projects. The ESP8266 is a low-cost Wi-Fi MCU chip with full TCP/IP stack and MCU features. Below are some of the Node-MCU specifications. Processor: 32-bit RISC microprocessor core L106, 10 dies based on Xtensa Diamond Standard 106Micro. Operating voltage: 3.3V Number of digital I/O pins: 17 Analog Input Pins: 1 (10-bit resolution) Clock Speed: 80 MHz or 160 MHz Flash: 4 MB or 16 MB Wi-Fi: 802.11 b/g/n

Antenna: Onboard PCB Antenna Connector for U. FL
 4 Channel Relay Technical Specifications are as follows:
 provides a voltage range of 3.75V - 6V.
 quiescent current is 2mA.

When the relay is working, the current is about 70mA. The maximum contact voltage of the relay is 250VAC / 30VDC.
 maximum current is 10A.

Fig. 3 Working Principal Flow Chart

Blynk is a popular Internet of Things (IoT) platform that allows developers to create applications to monitor and control smartphones, tablets or other Internet-enabled devices. Blynk provides a user-friendly interface for building mobile applications that can interact with various IoT devices such as microcontrollers, sensors, actuators, and other hardware devices. With Blynk, developers can create IoT apps by dragging and dropping widgets into a virtual mobile app, and then configure the widgets to communicate with connected devices on the Blynk Cloud or local Blynk server. Blynk supports multiple communication protocols such as Wi-Fi, Ethernet, Bluetooth and cellular, making it compatible with a wide variety of IoT devices and connectivity options.

Fig. 4(a) Blynk Desktop Interface Fig. 4(b) Blynk Mobile Interface

This is the Blynk IOT mobile and desktop interface. When connected to the Internet, such as a mesh connection, the system can be controlled from any software in the world. Blynk is an IoT platform that provides connectivity for writing or reading from hardware devices using a mobile application (Android or IOS). 1. The Blynk server is responsible for communication between the application (smartphone) and garden editing. Linking to the Blynk library supports commands written in-house and sent to the hardware.

Fig. 5 Working Condition of the Module

4.0 Special Features

- ✓ Home automation keeps your family comfortable.
- ✓ control over your home from any location.
- ✓ The greatest benefits of home automation system are added of sense of security and peace of mind.
- ✓ Voice control
- ✓ Remote access and control via smartphone app
- ✓ Smart lighting control
- ✓ Automated scheduling and routines
- ✓ Energy management and efficiency
- ✓ Integration with smart devices (e.g., Amazon Echo, Google Home)
- ✓ Advanced security features (e.g., motion detection, camera integration)
- ✓ Climate control (e.g., thermostat control)
- ✓ Home entertainment integration (e.g., TV, sound systems)
- ✓ Health and wellness monitoring (e.g., air quality, sleep tracking)

5.0 Result & Analysis

Successful implementation of automation systems such as lighting, temperature control, and appliance control. Improved convenience and comfort through remote control of devices. Energy savings through automation and scheduling of devices. NodeMCU provides a cost-effective solution for home automation due to its low cost and ease of programming. The platform's support for Wi-Fi connectivity enables remote control and monitoring of devices. The use of NodeMCU in home automation has led to increased adoption of smart home technologies and a growing market for related products. Home automation result analysis refers to the process of evaluating the performance and effectiveness of home automation systems. This analysis can involve various metrics such as energy savings, user satisfaction, reliability, and cost-effectiveness. The results of the analysis can be used to make informed decisions about future upgrades, maintenance, and usage of the home automation system. Home automation result analysis refers to the process of evaluating the performance and effectiveness of home automation systems. This analysis can involve various metrics such as energy savings, user satisfaction, reliability, and cost-effectiveness. The results of the analysis can be used to make informed decisions about future upgrades, maintenance, and usage of the home automation system. Home automation result analysis refers to the process of evaluating the performance and effectiveness of home automation systems. This analysis can involve various metrics such as energy savings, user satisfaction, reliability, and cost-effectiveness. The results of the analysis can be used to make informed decisions about future upgrades, maintenance, and usage of the home automation system. Home automation result analysis refers to the process of evaluating the performance and effectiveness of home automation systems. This analysis can involve various metrics such as energy savings, user satisfaction, reliability, and cost-effectiveness. The results of the analysis can be used to make informed decisions about future upgrades, maintenance, and usage of the home automation system.

6.0 Conclusion

As the name suggests, "home automation" systems make the system more flexible and user-friendly than other home automation systems. The system provides mobile and desktop web applications for home automation systems. It presents a modern architecture for home automation systems using an advanced communication technology. The system consists of three parts: WIFI module, Node-MCU and relay circuit. WIFI is used for communication between Node-MCU, Phone and Arduino microcontroller. This can hide the complexity of the ideas involved in home automation systems by closing them in a simple but connected set of related concepts. This simplification is about getting as much work done as possible in the limited space provided by mobile devices. This document provides a cost-effective, secure, ubiquitous, auto-configurable and remote-control solution. The communication method in the article is an uncommon and complete goal of using WIFI technology to control household appliances and connect household appliances to meet the needs and needs of users. Solutions with WIFI technology have proven to be remotely controlled, provide home security and are cost-effective compared to previous systems. Therefore, the device can conclude the home automation system has achieved its purpose. Design and construction methods are discussed, and basic technical procedures for control and remote monitoring of building materials are introduced. After all, it is a system introduced to commercialize a home automation system in terms of scalability and

flexibility.

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